

NFDI4Earth

Milestone MS1.4.1

Academy program has started, first events have been organized

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Executive summary

The Academy program for the first cohort started with our Kick-Off meeting on December 30th 2022. Till July 2023, we held a virtual lecture series, coffee lectures, a summer school and a Get-together at the NFDI4Earth Plenary in Dresden. A list of the events with a short description is provided in this document.

Contents

1 Kick-off meeting 2022	1
2 Cohort Calls 2023	2
3 Coffee lectures	2
4 Summer School 2023	5
5 DataXplorers cross-community Hackathon 2023	6
6 Think Tank 2023	8
7 NFDI4Earth Plenaries	9

1 Kick-off meeting 2022

Figure 1: Group photo of the meeting participants

From the 30th of November to the 02nd December 2022 the first NFDI4Earth Academy cohort held a Kick-Off retreat at castle Buchenau, close to Bad Hersfeld. It was the first get-together of the 39 fellows, and therefore mainly focused on getting-to-know each other and networking. The starting point for the intra- and interdisciplinary discussions was a poster session. Here the fellows presented their research topics with focus on the application of data science. Overlaps between topics and possibilities for collaborations were discussed.

To ensure and establish a good sense of community, as well as to foster a positive, open, and safe environment for all fellows within the Academy, guidelines of behavior and communication were identified. In various discussion rounds, the fellows expressed their ideas, expectations, and possible goals for the Academy. The content of courses and schools within the NFDI4Earth Academy program was a special focus of the discussions. Data Analysis, Machine/Deep Learning and Research Data Management have been identified as the three core areas of interest. Therefore, it was decided that the first school, which took place in June 2023, would address the topic of Machine Learning.

In the evenings, a night walk around the castle and a gathering around a fire bowl fostered further discussions and personal interactions.

2 Cohort Calls 2023

From the 10th February to the 21st April 2023, the Academy Fellows gathered for five lecture series sessions, which each lasted 1-1.5 hours and were held bi-weekly. In these participatory sessions, we explored open data science concepts, tools, and practical applications through exploring examples of research data management. The lessons aimed to improve data workflows, increase efficiency, and showcase collaborative research projects.

Session 1 Friday 10.02.2023 10:30-12:00 am - NFDI4Earth Pilots (Veronika Grupp, Uni Leipzig) & Introduction (Jonas Kuppler, GFZ Potsdam)

Session 2 Friday 24.02. 2023 10:30-12:00 am - Notebooks, Jupyter and Quarto (Dominik Hezel, Uni Frankfurt)

Session 3 Friday 10.03. 2023 10:30-12:00 am - Research software development & Docker for reproducible data science (Daniel Nüst, TU Dresden)

Session 4 Thursday 06.04. 2023 10:30-12:00 am - Describe Research Data/MetaData Kirsten Elger (GFZ Potsdam)

Session 5 Friday 21.04. 2023 10:30-12:00 am - Data management plans (Timm Schoening, GEOMAR) & Using GitLab for collaborative work (Thomas Rose, Universität Frankfurt)

3 Coffee lectures

The NFDI4Earth Academy offers its Online Coffee Lecture series on various topics related to Machine Learning, research data and the NFDI. This part of the NFDI4Earth Academy program is open to the whole community. Everybody is welcome and the participation is free of charge.

Monday 19.12.2022 11-12 am - Introducing the DataTrain-Program (Tanja Hörner, University Bremen Research Alliance)

Thursday 24.08.2023 11-12 am - Technical issues in data analytics: tips, tricks and hacks (Christoph Lehmann, TU Dresden)

Friday 08.09.2023 11-12 am - Introduction to NFDI4Earth IG High-performance Computing in Earth System Sciences (Stephan Frickenhaus, AWI) & IG Long-term Storage and Archiving (Tim Schürmann, BKG)

The Interest Groups are forum for the NFDI4Earth community to e.g. identify, discuss and communicate requirements for NFDI4Earth, jointly advance NFDI4Earth-related concepts, technologies and processes, implement NFDI4Earth principles, or to disseminate specific NFDI4Earth offers. Today both interest groups will briefly introduce themselves, their current work, goals and possibilities to join the activities.

Friday 22.09.2023 11-12 am - All you need to know about Software Licenses as a RSE (Tobias Schlauch, DLR)

A basic understanding of software licenses and related topics is necessary for RSEs to successfully publish their research software from the legal point of view. Typical questions are: What license should I use for code, documentation, or data? Can I combine this specific set of software licenses? How to document this information? This talk gives an overview about the copyright and software license basics. Using an example of a data analysis script written in Python, we go through the process of clarifying all relevant aspects and documenting them in a practical way. In this context, we introduce REUSE software which provides a standardized approach to document copyright and license information as well as helpful tools.

Friday 20.10.2023 11-12 am - Introduction to PANGAEA (Lars Möller, MARUM)

Friday 12.01.2024 11-12 am - GFZ Data Services (Kirsten Elger, GFZ)

GFZ Data Services is a repository for research data and scientific software across the Earth System Sciences, hosted at GFZ. The curated data are archived, persistently accessible and published with DOI. They range from large dynamic datasets from global monitoring networks with real-time acquisition, to international services in geodesy and geophysics, to the full suite of small and highly heterogeneous datasets collected by individual researchers or small teams ("long-tail data"). In addition to the DOI registration and data archiving itself, GFZ Data Services team offers comprehensive consultation by domain scientists and IT specialists.

This presentation will introduce to the broad service portfolio of GFZ Data Services, including project-specific DOI landing pages for our national and international partners, data curation practices, supporting tools like the online metadata editor, data description templates and extensive data publication guidelines. It will further show examples of how metadata exchange with other data portals is increasing the visibility of our data publications.

Wednesday 21.02.2024 11-12 am - Geo-INQUIRE (Fabrice Cotton, Stefanie Weege, GFZ)

Geo-INQUIRE (Geosphere INfrastructures for QUestions into Integrated REsearch) fosters excellent, interdisciplinary and curiosity-driven research of the solid Earth, including land-sea-atmosphere interfaces. The EU project benefits from a unique partnership of 51 European partners. Now, the 1st Geo-INQUIRE Transnational Access Call to European research infrastructures is open and provides access to unique high-level installations and experiments. Geo-INQUIRE is welcoming applications from researchers, technicians, students and other

specialists working in the fields of research covered by the installations. The call is open until 15 March 2024. In addition, Geo-INQUIRE offers online seminars, online training, on-site workshops, on-site summer schools and in the near future personalised training, all free of charge. We promote equality, diversity and inclusion in all Geo-INQUIRE activities. Therefore, applications from women and applications from people working in one of the widening countries, associated countries and outermost regions of Horizon Europe will be given special attention during the whole project life time.

Friday 08.03.2024 11-12 am - Inferring Causal Relationships from Data - An Introduction (Jonas Wahl, DLR & TU Berlin)

One of the primary goals of many research fields is to infer and describe causal relationships between scientific phenomena based on observational and experimental data. In the last decades, scientists and statisticians have developed a variety of formalisms as a scientific language for causal claims, as well as many algorithms that aim to infer causal networks or causal effects under different assumptions. I will give an introduction to the Causal Inference framework of Pearl and others and describe its current state-of-the-art with a particular focus on time series data.

Friday 22.03.2024 11-12 am - Explainable Machine Learning: Basics & Beyond (Lorenz Linhardt, TU Berlin)

Machine learning (ML) methods have become ubiquitous in the sciences. Despite their widespread usage, it is unclear what they learn and where they may fail. Explainable ML methods attempt to provide additional insights into the inner workings of ML models and their decision-making strategies. This talk will give a brief introduction to explainable ML, in particular well-established methods, and will provide pointers to more recent developments.

Friday 12.04.2024 11-12 am - The DataHub - empowering digital data-driven research
(Martin Hammitzsch, GFZ)

The DataHub, a collaborative effort across the seven research centers within the Research Field Earth and Environment of the Helmholtz Association, aims to break down data silos and empower research. This integrative initiative, anchored in the field's joint research program, brings together previously separate marine, terrestrial, and atmospheric research data into a single, open, and interoperable information hub. Following the FAIR principles, the DataHub will serve as a digital ecosystem for researchers to store, manage, share, and analyze their data across disciplines and institutions. It provides a federated data infrastructure and a suite of tools for advancing research digitalization and fostering a cultural shift within the field Earth and Environment. This interconnected and interoperable data infrastructure stands as a significant contribution to the National Research Data Infrastructure (NFDI) - notably, it will support NFDI4Earth.

Friday 26.04.2024 11-12 am - SIS MAPS (FID Karten) - Specialised Information Service Cartography and Geodata (Cornelia Koch & Martin Jeske, Staatsbibliothek zu Berlin)

The SIS Maps, located in the Map Department of the Staatsbibliothek zu Berlin (SBB) is funded by the German Research Foundation (DFG). The lecture will focus on the services of the SIS, which are aimed in particular at scientists of geoinformation but also at the interdisciplinary professional community who use maps. They include the largely digital provision of specialist information on cartographic materials (literature, glossary, maps and geodata) as well as infrastructures that enable them to be found and accessed (special catalogues, bibliography and repository).

4 Summer School 2023

Figure 2: Photo collage of the summer school with four pictures of a lecture, a break, a discussion, and people jointly working on laptops

The 2023 NFDI4Earth Academy Summer School took place from the 12th – 14th June at the FU Berlin and focused on Machine Learning. The fellows at the Academy Kick-Off chose the topic in December 2022. The cohort speakers Melina Knoke and Verena Maleska, as well

as Till Fohrmann and Nils Weitzel developed the program in cooperation with the Academy coordinators. 29 Academy fellows attended the Summer School.

The Summer School started on the 12th of June with an introduction to Machine Learning by Christoph Lehmann (TU Dresden), addressing common difficulties within Machine Learning and providing a common baseline of knowledge. Due to the diverse scientific background of the fellows, this topic was of particular interest.

On the 13th of June the day consisted of lectures and hands-on formats on temporal and spatial data. Karin Mora (University Leipzig) gave an overview of temporal data in Machine Learning and provided the fellows with an interesting data set on logistic maps. After lunch, Christopher Kadow (DKRZ) gave an overview of spatial data in Climate Science, and Johannes Meuer (DKRZ) and Maximilian Witte (DKRZ) provided the fellows with a hands-on experience of the topic. The day was closed by presentations from Maria Isabel Arango, Omar Seleem and Josephine Umlauf on Machine Learning in their own research projects. The evening program included a Pub Quiz with exciting and comical questions about the NFDI4Earth and facts about Earth Sciences.

On the 14th of June Maximilian Gelbrecht (TU Munich & PIK) held the final lecture, introducing physics-informed Machine Learning to the fellows.

5 DataXplorers cross-community Hackathon 2023

The pieces are falling into place - Accomplishments of the DataXplorers cross-community hackathon 2023.

Our [DataXplorers cross-community hackathon](#) concluded with an inspiring hybrid event on December 5 and 6 in Frankfurt am Main. Challenge providers, participants of the hackathon, and interested audiences from the community came together to present the accomplishments of their work, engage in discussions about future steps, and foster valuable connections. The event was joined by 20 in-person and 29 remote participants from 28 different institutions.

The hackathon was jointly organized by the NFDI4Earth Academy, NFDI4Biodiversity, and NFDI4Microbiota and focussed on developing tools and working on data bridging the different communities. The technical infrastructure was provided by [de.NBI](#). Several NFDI4Earth partners from the Bavarian State Archives (GDA), Bielefeld University, Leibniz Institute of Ecological Urban and Regional Development, Max Planck Institute for Biogeochemistry, and TU Dresden were planning and supervising the hackathon challenges. The DataXplorers hackathon started with an online kick-off event on October 23 and offered six challenges, four of which were actively pursued.

The teams achieved astonishing results within only six weeks of working time. All results, along

Figure 3: Photo collage of the summer school with four pictures of a breakout group discussion and project presentations

with a comprehensive report, will soon be made publicly available in the [DataExplorers Zenodo community](#). We extend our sincere gratitude to all participants, organizers, and partners for making the DataExplorers hackathon a success.

What was achieved in the challenges?

Challenge 2 was jointly organized by partners of the Bavarian State Archives and the Leibniz Institute of Ecological Urban and Regional Development (IOER). During the hackathon, three teams worked towards the aim of an automatic colour inspection of directories or collections of scanned historical maps, their sorting according to colour information, and the determination of land use classes. Each team found its own approach to tackling the challenge. Further, a total of 60 historical maps were digitized and will be made publicly available in the process.

In **challenge 3**, led by partners of the TU Dresden, the team developed a prototype version of a web- and large language model-based Q&A tool that assists researchers in finding answers on RDM topics. The goal is to further develop this prototype and to bring it to use in the context of an NFDI-wide service.

A more educational approach was pursued in **challenge 5**, organized by partners of the Max Planck Institute for Biogeochemistry, where several teams were introduced to work with data cubes. The teams learned how to link climatological datasets to species distribution data and, thus how to access data from different sources, and to combine vector data and data cubes.

Challenge 6 was led by partners of the Leibniz-Institut für Analytische Wissenschaften (ISAS) and developed the prototype of a user-friendly web service that transfers metaproteomics data into standard formats and enriches them with further information and metadata. The team continues working on improving the functionalities of the prototype and aims to make it available for other data types.

6 Think Tank 2023

On December 6-7, 2023, the first NFDI4Earth Academy Think Tank in Frankfurt emerged as a successful event, with the overarching goal of fostering common ground, exchanging ideas, and uncovering collaboration possibilities among participants. The event commenced with a cordial welcome and an introduction to the forthcoming NFDI4Earth Incubators Call, scheduled for spring.

The first day was dedicated to fostering creativity and exploring diverse techniques for idea generation. Following a theoretical overview of tools like "Reizworttechnik" and "Brainwriting Pool," participants organized themselves into thematic discussion rounds. Leveraging these tools, lively conversations about various topics arose roaming around Machine Learning and spatial data. Shared interests, such as automated workflows for aligning digital elevation

models were identified. The day concluded with a brief wrap-up session, leading to a convivial joint dinner and a casual get-together.

The second day started with a warm welcome and was followed by a third discussion round and two sessions on the upcoming Academy online school and the NFDI4Earth Plenary in May. The closing session provided a platform for general feedback, culminating in a convivial lunch that offered a final opportunity for networking and exchange before the participants departed.

7 NFDI4Earth Plenaries

Figure 4: Collage of four pictures with impressions of the NFDI4Earth plenary

On the **second NFDI4Earth Plenary** on June 1st 2023, we organized an informal Get-together with all Fellows attending the Plenary.

From 22th – 24th May 2024, we organized an informal Get-together, an Academy speed-dating, a poster session and a Workshop on “FAIR GPT for FAIR research data” open to all Fellows and participants of the **third NFDI4Earth Plenary**.

*On May 24, the NFDI4Earth Plenary featured an engaging workshop on the potential

of ChatGPT in research data management, attracting around 50-60 participants. Jonas Kuppler kicked off the session with an introduction to ChatGPT and prompt engineering fundamentals, setting the stage for Renat Shigapov's (University of Mannheim) detailed presentation on FAIR GPT (<https://chat.openai.com/g/g-BkMR28wIV-fair>). This innovative virtual consultant, integrated within ChatGPT Plus, aims to enhance the FAIR (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, and Reusable) management of research data. Renat Shigapov demonstrated practical applications of FAIR GPT in tackling real-world research data challenges, followed by a lively discussion where attendees posed questions and shared comments. The workshop highlighted how advanced AI tools can streamline research data management. For those interested in further exploration, documentation for FAIR GPT is available on GitHub (<https://github.com/UB-Mannheim/FAIR-GPT>).